

D7.6: Agricultural Insurance Enablers - Advisory Board report (3)

WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821964.

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Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	821964	Acronym	BEACON
Full Title	Boosting Agricultural Insurance based on Earth Observation		
Horizon 2020 Call	H2020-SPACE-2018		
Type of Action	IA		
Start Date	01/01/2019	Duration (in months)	37
EU Project Officer	Iulia SIMION		
Deliverable	D7.6: Agricultural Insurance Enablers – Advisory Board report (3)		
Work Package	WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M25	Actual M25
Nature	R – Report	Dissemination Level	PU – Public
Lead Beneficiary	ETAM		
Lead Author	Maroulla Schiza	Organization	ETAM
Other authors			
Reviewer(s)	KARAVIAS		

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	26-1-2021	Draft version	First integrated version	ETAM
2.0	28-1-2021	Draft version	Comments from KARAVIAS	KARAVIAS
3.0	31-1-2021	Final version	Incorporation of comments, finalization of document	ETAM

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List of Acronyms

Acronyms	Explanation
AB	Advisory Board
AgI	Agricultural Insurance
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
UA	Underwriting Agency
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The current Deliverable 7.6: "Agricultural Insurance Enablers (3)" Advisory Board report, provides an overview of the main discussion points and feedback received during the 3rd BEACON Agricultural Insurance (AgI) Enablers - reporting period. Specifically, it provides the board's expert opinion on the impact the pandemic has had in the AgI sector, as well as mitigation measures and opportunities presented for the project. This is the third of the four relevant deliverables that are being developed within the project timeline.

The document is structured in 5 chapters. Chapter 1 presents an overview of the AgI Enablers and their role within the project. Chapter 2 includes a small presentation of the BEACON AgI Enablers group. The feedback received by the AgI Enablers is presented in Chapter 3. The next chapter concludes the AgI Enablers recommendations, whilst the final Chapter of this deliverable presents planning of the next steps for the full elaboration of the AgI Enablers group, within the project.

All the activity related to the BEACON AgI Enablers – Advisory Board within the project duration, falls under the implementation of WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion, led by the project partner ETAM SA, and relative Deliverables (D7.4-7.7). The current deliverable D7.6 AgI Enablers -Advisory Board report (3) is the third deliverable and focuses on the impact the pandemic has had on agriculture and thus on AgI services. The first deliverable was submitted in Month 5 (May 2019), the second in Month 17 (May 2020). The final deliverable will be submitted in M37 (January 2022).

1. Introduction

BEACON Advisory Board "Agricultural Insurance Enablers" is a multi-actor group of stakeholders of high expertise in policy, regulatory, technical, scientific, commercial as well as socio-economic aspects of the project. The AgI Enablers AB aims at providing advice and guidance throughout the project's timeline in order to support the development of the project and ensure results of high quality. The AB additionally aims at establishing synergies towards an AgI enabled environment as well as discussing challenges and opportunities arising in the Agricultural Insurance. At the same time, the AgI Enablers group will be exploited as a high-end dissemination channel for the diffusion of BEACON advancements and outcomes, multiplying networks of different segments for the BEACON market exploitation and also supporting active engagement in the project activities.

The AgI Enablers members role includes:

- ⊗ participation in at least one conference call per year (upon request of the project);
- ⊗ provide ad-hoc feedback when requested by the project consortium (or the project officer);
- ⊗ provide written feedback and advice to BEACON partners on the quality of the results achieved throughout the implementation of the BEACON project;
- ⊗ review of project deliverables and identify strengths and weaknesses with respect to the objectives of the project and the intended impact, and to provide written feedback.

The current COVID-19 pandemic has already disrupted production and marketing of agricultural goods all around the world. These disruptions have affected all scales and markets of agriculture, and the farmers, whilst crop insurance has also faced a series of specific challenges. Additionally, COVID-19 has also changed the daily operations of the insurance companies and adaptations need to be made, for instance, regarding on-the-spot inspections and payments.

Insurance has to be seen in a new light, given the recent developments. With the pandemic bringing an additional focus on agriculture and allied activities, there is a need to consider how insurance coverage can support the sector. To this end it was deemed necessary that the input requested from the AB over this period should concentrate on the impact the pandemic has had on the Agricultural Insurance and the opportunities the project presents to mitigate its effect on the sector.

2. Members of the BEACON AgI Enablers

As described in the first and second deliverable the six (6) members of the BEACON AgI Enablers group as established by Month 17, are:

Dr. Ioannis Athanasiadis is an Associate Professor at Wageningen University, Netherlands. His expertise lies with geo-information science, artificial intelligence, intelligent information systems, metadata and ontologies

Dr. Clement Atzberger is Full Professor and Head of the Institute of Surveying, Remote Sensing and Land Information of BOKU University in Vienna and an expert for proper RS data pre-processing & time series analysis.

Mr. Christopher Genillard is owner and Managing Director of Genillard & Co. GmbH, focusing on building and establishing innovative new business models and insurance products

Mr. Paul Meeusen is a specialist provider of treasury, cash management and financial planning software and Blockchain. He is a Strategic Consultant to the B3i Board - Blockchain Insurance Industry Initiative.

Ms. Shilpa Pankaj is Vice president with Guy Carpenter's Asia Pacific team based out of London. She has years of experience in dealing with insurance and reinsurance companies engaged in agriculture re/insurance business across Asia and Europe.

Mrs. Eleni Vakaki is an Earth Observation expert - index insurance specialist at EARS/eLEAF a remote sensing company in Netherlands, with expertise in agriculture and water management.

3. Interviews overview

The COVID-19 crisis is the definitive global health crisis of our time, with a potential to create an unprecedented socio-economic crisis. According to numerous publications, the pandemic has significantly disrupted production and marketing of agricultural goods globally, entraining the agricultural insurance market.

The AgI Enablers group, is a group of experts of the AgI insurance sector that are close to the developments of the sector and are in direct contact with the market offering the project an insider's view. To this end – and following the impacts of the unexpected outbreak – planning for the AB contribution was altered as priorities have changed. The input considered necessary over this period was to examine the challenges Agri-insurance (AgI) companies are currently facing and look into mitigation actions.

An interview for each member of the advisory board based on an adhoc structured questionnaire according to their expertise was organised. The goal was to collect their feedback on the impact the pandemic has had on the different sectors relative to AgI and insights on how to turn the difficulties faced at these unprecedented times in opportunities for the project's and the sector's benefit.

Given the difficulties everyone is facing at the time on a personal and professional level, it was not possible to receive feedback from all the members of the AgI Enablers Group. Nonetheless several interesting and useful recommendations were provided by some of the members of the AB which are summarized in the following sections.

The Questions presented to the AgI Enablers that did not manage to respond are presented in the annex and remain to be investigated on. In the following the answers received by the participating AgI Enablers, are presented.

3.1 Interview with Mrs. Eleni Vakaki

The main points of the interview with Mrs. Eleni Vakaki are presented in the following:

How has the agricultural sector been impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic?

As governments focus their resources on the war against the pandemic, they fail to take the measures needed to adapt to the impacts of climate breakdown which are pushed further down in their political agenda. As a result, this increases the exposure of farmers to adverse weather events and leads to the increase of poverty and hunger in the developing world. At the same time, due to the pandemic farmers' income from selling their crop has been reduced. From our experience as eLEAF and from discussions with our partners in Africa we see that the agriculture sector, especially in Africa, has been largely impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic. Due to the travelling limitations, farmers' access to inputs and financial services was restricted. Insurance agents were not able to travel as well, and as a result the sales volumes in 2020

has decreased. For now, we don't observe any decrease in the international funds for insurance projects, but I believe this is going to be the case the following years.

In response to the impact of the pandemic, what are your expectations for agricultural insurance?

We expect, that insurance uptake will remain somewhat limited the coming semester and will pick up again from the second semester 2021. Moreover, the impact of the pandemic to farmers' income is expected to reduce their ability and willingness to pay for crop insurance, so the premiums may have to be accordingly adjusted in order to offer viable products. This will have as a result, on the one hand limited coverage for the farmers and on the other hand the margin for the insurance and data providers may decrease. However, this is an educated guess, since the whole world is still expecting to see the long-term impact of the pandemic in all sectors.

Could Index-based insurance in agriculture be correlated to the effects of the pandemic?

As already mentioned, the pandemic has affected the uptake of index insurance. That means that likely less farmers are covered against adverse weather events and are therefore prone to big financial losses. Nevertheless, compared to traditional indemnity-based insurance which involves much more travel, farm visits and loss assessments, index insurance remains more flexible and the only solution that can still work, especially in remote parts of the world.

What solutions to the problems identified could be offered by the support of EO technologies?

EO technologies and applications add significant value to the agriculture sector, since they assist farmers mitigate, manage or transfer their risk. Increasing farmers' resilience and supporting them will be more important than ever, so I believe EO will continue playing an important role. However, it is important that the political agendas keep and increase their focus on climate change and adaptation in order to allow efficient and financially sustainable solutions using EO data to be developed and ensure their distribution and uptake from producers.

3.2 Interview with Mr. Christopher Genillard

Mr. Christopher Genillard started off by explaining the following:

A July 2020 analysis by FAO and WFP identified 27 countries – no world region is immune - that are on the frontline of impending COVID-19-driven food crises, as the pandemic's knock-on effects aggravate pre-existing drivers of hunger.

How has the agricultural insurance sector been impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic?

Through our direct contact with agro-insurers in Europe we see little or no impact of COVID-19 on their business in general terms in 2020. The vulnerable groups include small-scale farmers, migrant and informal workers, who are mostly uninsured.

 What were the main challenges faced over this period and mainly over lockdown periods?

Loss adjusting for damaged crops out in the field requires social contact from adjuster to farmer, and insurance companies issued new guidelines how it should be conducted (social distancing, wearing of masks, etc.) This will accelerate digital loss adjusting through remote sensing processes, such as those being developed in the BEACON project.

 What measures have agricultural insurance companies taken to support farmers over the pandemic?

In some cases, allowing a delayed payment of premiums.

 How has the risk profile of farmers been impacted by COVID-19?

Farmers have faced challenges accessing markets to sell their products or buy essential inputs, or struggle due to higher food prices and limited purchasing power. Informal laborers have been hard hit by job and income losses in harvesting and processing.

 The COVID-19 lockdown has impacted farmers due to the disruption of agricultural inputs, access to markets as well as delays in harvest and planting. How can the Agri insurance sector respond to farmers emerging needs?

This question should be put to governments and the other players in the agriculture value chain! To support farmers and their organisations in the coming months, it is important to allow movement of seasonal workers and transport operators across domestic and international borders. Another good practice would be to identify collection centers closer to producers, for example develop storage facilities like warehouse receipt system platforms where farmers can deliver their produce without the need to go to markets. If possible, allow local markets to remain open, while putting in place strict physical distancing measures within and outside markets. If feasible, relocate markets to larger premises, while ensuring the appropriate infrastructure is in place to maintain quality and food safety.

3.3 Interview with Mr. Paul Meeusen

The main points of the interview with Mr. Paul Meeusen are presented in the following:

 How has the agricultural sector been impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic?

Covid-19 has re-iterated the fragility of global supply chains in favor of local supply. I believe that increasingly people will look for high quality, bio agricultural products, wherever possibly supplied locally.

Has the pandemic changed the Agri companies' familiarization with digital tools for the provision of Agri services?

I have seen small and medium sized farmers using digital tools (from e-commerce to cash free payment systems for direct sales on the farm) to distribute their products during the pandemic. Again, a sign of local supply trying to become more independent from the mass supply chains.

What are the lessons learned and what do you think are the important next steps / mitigation measures that need to be taken for the future?

Some research starts establishing a correlation between the C19 virus and potential viruses increasing in our bio-sphere. Under that hypothesis, C19 is seen as only a first example of a wider problem that is coming our way, caused by having disrupted (if not almost destroyed) the natural eco-system. Again, I believe, this will further increase skepticism towards large scale, industrial agriculture (e.g. mono culture) which has caused this.

Could new technologies such as EO and Blockchain support the Agri sector to manage shortcomings faced over the pandemic and especially over lock down periods?

Digital tools should probably be used to assess the risk described above, and mitigate it from further spreading.

4. AgI Enablers Recommendations

A summary of recommendations / important aspects highlighted by the AgI Enablers, regarding the impact of the pandemic are presented in the table below. Their comments are linked to specific mitigation actions that the BEACON project has to offer to the AgI sector. Relevant recommendations will be considered by the project partners in the realization of the project activities.

Name	Identified pandemic impacts / Recommendations	BEACON Mitigation Actions
Mrs Eleni Vakaki	Insurance agents faced difficulties in promoting products due to restrictions in travelling which resulted in a decrease in sales volumes.	<p>The BEACON climatology service can provide the needed information to insurance agents so as to offer the “right” product to the potential client, even if physical presence or meeting would be impossible during COVID-19 situation.</p> <p>Enabling the insurance agents to provide the most appropriate product, in terms of costs and coverages, while having access to all related information would allow the insurance company to profitably serve the customers through an online channel.</p>
	Farmers suffered losses in their income and are thus expected to be more reluctant to invest in insurance products. Insurance Prices need to be adjusted.	The reduction of travelling and minimization of administrative costs can offer the AgI the ability to adjust their pricing policies. This can be tackled both by the implementation of the BEACON tool and the business models for sustainable growth and commercialization strategy of WP6.
	Index insurance is found to be more flexible and preferable for remoted areas.	The overall aim of WP3 is to develop services based on earth observation products and atmospheric data. BEACON can serve either index/ parametric insurance scheme or calamity based one.

Name	Identified pandemic impacts / Recommendations	BEACON Mitigation Actions
Mr Christopher Genillard	<p>New social distancing rules are expected to accelerate digital loss adjusting as in field estimates are difficult.</p>	<p>The need to reduce the number of on-site visits for claim verification, in order to reduce operational and administrative costs for monitoring of insured indexes has become a necessity due to the pandemic. As Christopher is describing this should accelerate BEACON's uptake as social contacts (farmer – insurer) due to pandemic have been minimised.</p>
	<p>Farmers have suffered income losses in harvesting and processing and in some cases Agri companies supported farmers by allowing delayed payments of premiums.</p>	<p>Given that farmers have suffered income losses Agri companies are in turn expected to be impacted. BEACON will reduce operational and administrative costs for monitoring of insured indexes and contract handling, and design more accurate and personalized contracts thus supporting Agri companies through this crisis.</p>

Name	Identified pandemic impacts / Recommendations	BEACON Mitigation Actions
Mr. Paul Meeusen	<p>Small and medium sized farmers have had to familiarize themselves with digital tools over the pandemic.</p>	<p>The uptake of digital tools over the pandemic by a number of small and medium scale farmers is significant for the successful uptake of BEACON's tool. This is a positive impact of the pandemic for the Agri sector, as it will allow Agri companies to use digital tools more widely. To support, the different actors' sizes and requirements in terms of services, BEACON allows the modular provision of its services. The "Go to the market strategy" also examines and evaluates companies IST and presents integration solutions in different markets.</p>

Climate change and various emergency situations, as well as the COVID-19 pandemic, are among the challenges currently facing Agri-insurance (Agl) companies. Investing in research is a key to developing the best solutions.

The BEACON research project aims to develop a bundle of commercial tools and services for the Agl companies:

- a) supporting them to achieve a better risk and damage assessment within their Agl products,
- b) enabling them to reduce the number of on-site visits for claims verification and to reduce their overall operational and administrative costs for monitoring and handling Agl contracts and
- c) allowing them to design more accurate and personalized contracts.

In the case of COVID-19, the BEACON Toolbox is designed to make the logistic work in the agri-insurance company more efficient, improving the staff distribution tasks through a better overview of damages that occurred.

5. Next steps

In the next period of the project (M24-M36) and following the project developments, a teleconference is to be planned and organized that aims at providing the project developments on the BEACON toolbox, pilot implementation and initial business models to the AgI Enablers group. This teleconference aims to present the project developments, review progress of project activities, allow the dynamic interaction with the project partners addressing strategic questions and plan for the coming periods. If needed, ad-hoc teleconferences with the AgI Enablers group will be held to discuss on particular issues developed.

In person meetings with the AgI Enablers group had been planned but the pandemic put a halt on them. Current planning does not include in person meetings. They could be potentially organized, or even the AgI Enablers members could participate in project progress meetings and events once it is safe to do so. The schedule of BEACON project meetings and relevant events will be shared with the AgI Enablers members and will be further discussed to identify and agree the participation of any members. The BEACON consortium partners have mutually agreed and allocated budget to cover travel expenses (flight and accommodation) for the AgI Enablers members.

Meeting reports, summarizing the overall discussions, conclusions, observations on project results and recommendations on actions for impact creation will be prepared after each meeting with the AgI Enablers members and group. Input of these reports is presented in the tasks relevant deliverables (D7.4-D7.7). ETAM, being responsible of the implementation of the AgI Enablers related activities (Task 7.3 – Agricultural Insurance Enablers: BEACON Advisory Board), ensures that the conclusions and recommendations are adequately taken into consideration by the Project Coordinator and the project consortium throughout the decision-making process all along the project life span.

